

The new spectrophotometric methods for the estimation of Butorphanol tartarate in bulk and pharmaceutical formulations

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Abstract : Six simple and sensitive spectrophotometric methods (I, II, III, IV, V and VI) in the visible region have been developed for the quantitative estimation of Butorphanol tartarate in bulk drug and pharmaceutical formulations. These methods are based on the reaction of oxidative coupling reaction with 3-methyl-2-benzothiazolinone hydrazone (MBTH), 1,10-phenanthroline, ferric chloride Gibb's reagents, FC reagent, and potassium ferricyanide to form green, red, dark colored, bluish green, dark colored and bluish green chromogen with absorption maxima at 424 nm, 515 nm, 795 nm, 588 nm, 756.5 nm and 786 nm Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range of 5–25 µg/ml, 5–25 µg/ml, 1–5 µg/ml, 5–25 µg/ml, 2–12 µg/ml and 1–5 µg/ml respectively. The results of analysis have been validated statistically and by recovery studies. The methods were found to be accurate, precise, rapid, and economic.

Keywords : Butorphanol tartarate, spectrophotometric methods, 1,10-phenanthroline, MBTH.

Introduction

Butorphanol tartarate¹ is chemically (-)-17-(cyclobutyl methyl)morphan-3,14-diol hydrogen tartrate and it is non-narcotic analgesic. It is phenanthrene derivative, which is an opioid analgesic and antagonist properties. It is used for relief of moderate to severe pain and as an adjunct to anesthesia and it is official in United State of Pharmacopeia (USP). Butorphanol tartrate is available as a nasal spray formulation, normally taken as a 1 or 2 mg dose, which provides rapid relief of pain symptoms lasting for 5–6 h². This formulation has proved effective in managing pain such as that suffered in migraine attacks or severe headaches³ and has been used in cases of dental maxillofacial or other surgical pain^{4,5}. Investigation of some needed for the quantitative estimation of Butorphanol in bulk and pharmaceutical formulation. A few analytical methods have been reported for its quantitative estimation in pharmaceutical formulation, which include HPLC, HPTLC, and microbiological analysis^{6,7}. Assay methods for Butorphanol in clinical plasma samples that have been

reported to date have included radioimmunoassay (RIA)⁸ and gas chromatography (GC) with mass spectrometry (MS) detection⁹. While both of these methods are sensitive enough to quantitate Butorphanol. In view of the above fact, some simple analytical methods are needed for its quantitative estimation. In the present work, four simple and sensitive spectrophotometric methods have been developed for the quantitative estimation of Butorphanol tartarate in bulk and pharmaceutical formulation.

Results and discussion

The colored chromogens produced by the reactions are shown in Scheme 1 absorb radiations in the visible region of spectrum, but wavelength and absorptivity depend on the structure of the aromatic groups, pH and solvent. The determination conditions for all the methods were established by varying one parameter at a time and keeping others fixed by the observing the effect produced on the absorbance of the colored species. The various parameters involved for maximum color development for all the methods were optimized. The absorbance values

in all four methods were measured at time intervals of 20 min for 8 h to find out the stability of the formed chromogen and it was found that the chromogen was stable for more than 8 h in all the methods. The proposed methods were validated statistically and by recovery studies.

The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity values conforms the sensitivity of all the four methods, while the precision is confirmed by the % Relative standard deviation (RSD). Results have been showed in Table 2. Assay results and recovery studies results are given in the Table 1. The results are in good agreement with labeled values. The present recovery obtained indicates non-interference from the common excipients used in the formulations. The reproducibility, repeatability and accuracy of the methods were found to be good, which is evidenced by low standard deviation. The proposed meth-

ods were simple, sensitive, accurate, precise and reproducible and can be successfully applied for the routine estimation of Butorphanol tartarate in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage forms.

Experimental

Gift sample of Butorphanol tartarate was obtained from Aristo Laboratories Ltd., Mumbai, India. All chemicals were AR grade purchased from Qualigens, Mumbai, India.

Preparation of standard solutions :

Butorphanol tartarate standard stock solutions (1 mg/ml) were prepared by dissolving 100 mg of pure drug in 100 ml of standard flask with distilled water. Ferric chloride (0.5%) w/v and, (0.03 M), MBTH (0.2% w/v) and 1.10 phenanthroline (0.10 M), ceric ammonium sulphate

Scheme 1

Table 1. Results of analysis of Butorphanol tartarate in injectables

Formulation (mg) injectables	Label claim	Method	% of label claim*	% Recovery*
I ₁	1.0	I	99.92 ± 0.123	99.32 ± 0.321
I ₂	1.0	II	99.52 ± 0.621	99.02 ± 0.234
I ₃	1.0	III	99.75 ± 0.023	99.15 ± 0.550
I ₄	1.0	IV	99.67 ± 0.123	99.92 ± 0.023
I ₅	1.0	V	99.02 ± 0.065	99.12 ± 0.044
I ₆	1.0	VI	99.46 ± 0.012	99.01 ± 0.871

*SD = Standard deviation, mean ± SD ($n = 5$).

(100 mg Butorphanol was added and recovered)

Table 2. Optical and regression characteristics of Butorphanol tartarate in different methods

Parameters	Method	Method	Method	Method	Method	Method
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI
Wavelength maxima (λ_{\max})	425	515	795	588	756.5	786
Beer's law limits ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	5–25	5–25	1–5	5–25	2–12	1–5
Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g/cm}^{-1}/0.001$)	0.054	0.0942	0.00510	0.20	0.0392	0.01
Molar absorptivity ($\text{L/mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	8.09×10^3	5.09×10^3	9.865×10^3	1.660×10^3	1.193×10^4	7.306×10^4
Correlation coefficient (r^2)	0.9989	0.9990	0.9999	0.9992	0.9996	0.9932
Regression coefficient (y^*):						
Slope (a)	0.0165	0.0114	0.1034	0.0231	0.0224	0.0165
Intercept (b)	0.0112	0.0004	0.213	0.0032	0.0031	0.0101
Range of errors:						
Confidence limit with 0.05 level	0.0023	0.001	0.0013	0.0031	0.00209	0.002896
Confidence limit with 0.01 level	0.0035	0.0025	0.0055	0.0050	0.00310	0.004285
Relative standard deviation (%)	0.550	1.4532	0.2542	0.4532	1.002	0.5660

$Y^* = a + Bc$, where C is the concentration of butorphanol tartarate in $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and Y is the absorbance at the respective λ_{\max} .

*SD = standard deviation; mean ± SD ($n = 5$).

Average ± standard deviation of five determination (known quantity of the standard was added in the solution of ampoule and then final solution were analyzed).

(1% w/v) and Gibb's reagent (0.2% w/v) were prepared by double distilled water.

Method I :

Colorimetric method using MBTH : Aliquots of Butorphanol tartarate ranging from 0.5–2.5 ml were transferred in to series of 10 ml volumetric flasks. To each flask, 3 ml of ceric ammonium sulphate and 3 ml of MBTH (0.2% w/v) were added to stand for 15 min to develop color. The volumes were made up to mark with water. The absorbance of colored chromogen was measured at 424 nm against reagent blank the color was stabled for more than 8 h. The amount of drug present in the sample were computed from the calibration curve.

Method II :

Colorimetric method using 1,10-phenanthroline : Aliquots of drug ranging from 0.1–0.5 ml were transferred in to series of 10 ml volumetric flasks. To each flask, 0.2 ml of ferric chloride (0.03 M) and 0.5 ml of 1,10-phenanthroline (0.01 M) were added and heated on water bath for 30 min and the absorbance of blood red colored chromogen was measured at 515 nm.

Method III :

Colorimetric method using 2,2-bipyridine : Aliquots of drug ranging from 0.1–0.5 ml were transferred in to series of 10 ml volumetric flasks. The pure drug treated with 0.2 ml of ferric chloride and 1 ml of 2,2-bipyridine

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(0.01 M) to form dark green colored chromogen exhibiting absorption at 795 nm.

Method IV :

Colorimetric method using Gibb's reagent : Aliquots of drug ranging from 0.5–2.5 ml were transferred in to series of 10 ml volumetric flasks. To each flask add 0.5 ml (0.2% w/v) of Gibb's reagent and 1 ml of sodium nitrate (0.5 % w/v) were added the absorbance of colored chromogen were measured at 588 nm.

Method V :

Colorimetric method using Folin-Ciocalteu (FC) reagent : Aliquots of drug ranging from 2–12 ml were transferred in to series of 10 ml volumetric flasks. To each flask add 0.5 ml (0.5% w/v) of FC reagent and 0.5 ml phosphomolybdate tungstic acid were added the absorbance of colored chromogen were measured at 756.5 nm.

Method VI :

Colorimetric method using potassium ferricyanide reagent : Aliquots of drug ranging from 1–5 ml were transferred in to series of 10 ml volumetric flasks. To each flask add 0.5 ml (0.2% w/v) of reagent were added the absorbance of colored chromogen were measured at 786 nm.

Estimation from injectables :

In the present study one branded commercially available injectables were estimated by the proposed methods. The contents of five vials each containing 1 mg of drug were mixed thoroughly and volume equivalent to 100 mg of drug were pipette out and made up to 100 ml with distilled water. 10 ml of solution were diluted to 100 ml

in a volumetric flask to get a final concentration of 100 µg/ml in water. Aliquots of drug solution were taken and the individual assay procedure was followed for the estimation of drug content in the injectables. The concentration of drug in the injectables was calculate using calibration curve. The recovery experiments were carried out by standard addition method. The results of the analysis are given in Table 1.

Conclusion

A set of seven simple, sensitive, accurate and precise spectrophotometric methods has been developed. The presently developed method is that they are economical. These can be used for the routine determination of Butorphanol tartarate in bulk sample and in the pharmaceutical formulation.

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